

Application for survey permit _____ Draught copy

I wish to examine the archaeological evidence for long distance trade and for change in the commercial patterns in Southern Iran from the 9c A.D. until the period of Shah Abbas the Great.

I have studied the available information from contemporary Persian, Arabic, and European writers and will attempt to locate the routeways and archaeological sites indicated at different periods in these sources.

I intend to make a record of all sites visited by noting the size and location, by collecting a representative selection of the surface pottery and porcelain, and by the recording of standing monuments especially those such as caravanserais directly related to the major trading role of this area.

The aims of my study are;

- 1) To build up a picture of the major trade routes used at different periods.
- 2) Examination and recording of the major commercial centres especially those on the Persian Gulf.
- 3) To trace the distribution of pottery types in relation to these routes.

I hope to start field work in the middle of September 1968 by examining sites in the area of Kerman, moving in October to Shiraz and examining the routes between these two centres.

In November I intend to travel East along the overland trade route to Pakistan. December and January I will spend with the B.I.P.S. excavation at Siref. February, March and April 1969 I will study the sites on the shores and islands of the Persian Gulf.

a. williamson august 1968

Oct - Feb 1970

Survey Programme

For numbered routes please see map)

A. Mid-September to mid-December

- 1, 2. Each of two major Islamic routes Yazd to Kerman.
- 3. Routes from Kerman to Khorasan (as far as the northern border of Kerman province).
- 4. Route to Bam.
- 5, 6. Various routes from Kerman to Sirjan and Jiruft.
- 7, 8. Study of alternative Islamic routes from Kerman to Shiraz passing either North or South of Lake Baktegan.
Examination of major Islamic sites in Marv Dasht and Shiraz plain
- 9, 10, 11. Cursory study of each of three major Islamic routes from Shiraz to Isfahan as far as the border of Fars.
- 12, 13, 14, 15. Routes from Shiraz to the South: Firuzabad (12), Darab (13), Lar (14), and Furg (15).

B. Beginning of February to mid-April

- Visiting Islamic coastal sites (from west to east): Jannaba, Bandar Rik, Rishahr, Nakilu, Bandar Lengeh, Bandar Congo, Bandar Abbas, Minab.
- Visiting Islamic island sites (from west to east): Kais, Basidu, Qishm, Henjam, Hormuz.
- 16, 17, 18. Study of Islamic routes from Bandar Abbas to Lar (16), Jiruft (17) and Furg (18).
- 19. Study of the route along the Persian Gulf coast (19).